

THE ROLE OF SPEECH PURITY IN THE ACTIVITY OF A MODERN TEACHER

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Abstract. *At present, much attention is paid to the issues of scientific research on the problems of language and speech, the features of their connection with culture, which are considered a means of human communication. In connection with the development of society, the mutual exchange of ideas, as well as the rise of culture, directly depend on the characteristics of language and speech. This article explores the linguistic, psycholinguistic features of youth jargon. And explores the jargons used in the daily process of communication in the Uzbek language. It cites the jargon words of the younger generation, who are the main strata of society, and explains the importance and need of learning their jargon.*

Keywords: *language, jargon, slang, linguistics, speech, society, study, communication, vocabulary, system, youth, group, national, dictionary.*

Introduction. Today it is important to study the features of speech, language, which are considered a means of communication. The national language is a priceless blessing given to man by nature and society, which reflects the history, culture, creativity and human qualities of the people. The development of the language, the expansion of consumption depends on the people who speak this language, in particular, the literary language is a weapon of interaction between people and society. The civilization of our society is closely connected with changes and renewal, the emergence of languages and the expansion of its consumption. Consequently, this process is clearly visible in the reflection of historical processes, phenomena in the language and its transmission through the language to society.

It cannot be denied that every language serving a socially developed community of people is formed in different manifestations, especially secondary social dialects (slang, jargon, slang), professional languages are widely used in oral speech.

Main part. The national thinking and peculiarities of behavior characteristic of a person are manifested in the peculiarities of the language, in particular, its vocabulary. The language skill and speech actions reflect the most promising social stratum that determines the development directions of other social subsystems of the language, in particular, the features of speech pronunciation and the literary language.

Non-literary words are considered an integral part of the richness of the vocabulary language. Youth jargon as the language of everyday communication of youth expresses their level of development, interests, tastes and needs. Especially the speech of schoolchildren and students, closely associated with socio-economic and political reforms in the social life of the country, has the highest level of change and circle of influence.

There are social, economic and psychological roots in the dynamic nature of the speech process of users of the modern national language of the last decade. At the same time, the speech actions of people speaking the national language perform the function of a changing mirror of

social development. This feature of the modern national language as an ever-growing language means is seen as a positive development, because it provides a choice for those who speak their native language, and this, in turn, shows an increased potential to meet the needs for a certain connection of the national language.

The use of jargon is a limited vocabulary (French jargon - sheva) [10. 125]. Units that are used mainly in oral speech and whose meaning others in most cases do not understand are called jargon, those who by profession, place in society, interests, age form a separate social group.

At this stage, slang words in the national (Uzbek) language, which are currently used in the educational process, are given as an example.

Euro - means a Russian group (i.e. a group with Russian-speaking education). It is known that in the educational process, since training and classes are conducted in different languages, groups are divided according to the languages in which training is carried out. For example, groups such as English, German, Korean, Uzbek. Russian groups are considered one of them. Russian groups in the process of communication are called Euro group, euro potok. Only the word euro has its own definition in the Explanatory Dictionary of the Uzbek language, which differs from the slang meaning. The meaning of the word euro (from the name of the European continent) is the monetary unit of the members of the European Economic and Monetary Community within the European Union, put into circulation on January 1, 1999. The exchange rate of the som against the euro is indicated in the Explanatory Dictionary of the Uzbek Language [10. Б.Е.5]. This jargon does not have an emotional connotation, it is considered a word with a neutral meaning. For example: *I handed over my documents in euro flow. Do you have a euro lesson?*

Nats - Uzbek groups, a type of group in which lessons are taught in Uzbek. In this case, the slang word "nats" comes from the checkered form of the Russian word "national". "National. 1. see nation. 2. Characteristic for this nation, peculiar to it. National culture. N. tongue. N. theater. N. suit. 3. full f. The same as the state (in 1 value). N. flag. N. income. II noun nationality. [8. 988]. National - about nationality, nationality; National; national question; National action, given the meanings given by the Russian-Uzbek Dictionary of the Soviet Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan [9. 614]. There is no emotional coloring in this jargon either, it is a neutral word. For example: *Where is the National Stream located? Room not found for Nazis.*

The queen of the hall is a student girl who does not come to class at school. That is, it is a slang word that is used to describe girls who do not like to attend classes, are slow in learning subjects, have little interest in classes, do not want to submit to discipline, misbehave, are sometimes excluded from classes or for some reason, are late for classes and not included in classes. It consists of two combinations of words. The first word - "Hall" - means a house, or a spacious (large) hotel [9. T1. 322]. In the Explanatory Dictionary of the Uzbek language, the hall is taken from the word "saal" from the German language, which indicates the meaning of a large room, not shared [10. B.Z.126]. But this slang word was used to express the meaning of a long corridor between school classes. The queen in the next second word "queen" is expressed in the Uzbek explanatory dictionary in the meaning of a woman - KING [10. Б.М.533]. According to the dictionaries, this slang expression exactly corresponds to the meaning of "the woman king of the hotel." But this jargon has an emotional connotation, it is considered a word with a negative connotation, so this jargon is used in a critical, demonstrative sense. For example: *the queen of the hall is approaching. Do you want to be the queen of the hall again?*

Bigiz (head of bigiz) - knowing. A group with a lot of knowledge in the classroom, smart students are said to be "your own" in jargon because their thinking is considered strong. Bigiz - a shoemaker's tool, a metal tool with a pointed tip, with a wooden handle, used to pierce the skin, is described in the Explanatory Dictionary of the Uzbek language [10. B.B.252]. This jargon has the property of emotional coloring, and it is considered a positive word that is used in the sense of respect and envy (Havas and khurmat). For example: Call it Big, everyone will find the answer to this question. The Olympics will go to the head of the head. [1. 24].

Motherland - a smart student or pupil, activists. Excellent and well-trained in groups, disciplined, passionate about teamwork, active boys and girls are defined by the word homeland (patriot). Motherland - place of birth, Motherland. The country in which a person was born and raised and considers himself a citizen is expressed in the explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language [10. B. V. 444]. For example: this homeland made me mad. Motherland is always ready. Another Motherland has joined our group. This jargon has an emotional connotation, it is considered a word with a negative connotation, so this jargon is used in a critical, demonstrative sense.

Based on research, the psycholinguistic features inherent in a number of slang words are analyzed from the point of view of the scientific factor. The results of this analysis revealed a number of data. First of all, the true meaning of jargon and literary words is determined. The language features, comparability, the essence of figurative usage, etc. have been clarified. Linguistic features, analogy, essence of application in a figurative sense are defined as such. Attention is also focused on how the word jargon is formed: from which language it is taken, the vocabulary of abbreviations, etc. From the psychological characteristics it is revealed: by whom it is used, their age, gender, group, social status, potential, character traits, activities, etc. are manifested. It is understood that verbal slang is characterized by emotional coloring. In addition, it is noticed that slangs include features associated with the era, nation and nationalities.

In the social sense, slang is the creation of a cultural (civilized) environment that is natural for a person in everyday life, it forms a system of statuses, directions and requirements, determined by the range of concepts and symbols often found in speech.

Conclusion and recommendation. It is advisable for the teacher to pay attention to the slang (argo) of young people in the process of communication. For this reason, it is important to see the true nature of the student's speech culture. The teacher, whether he wants it or not, is a friend, guide, leader and, most importantly, a mentor for children, adolescents and youth, not only from the outside, but also from the inside. An educator is a leader who can explain positive authorities and values based on human understanding.

Modern educators today must know the spirituality of young people as deeply as possible and enter as deeply as possible into their circle. In this case, the teacher will correctly use his powers, will have an exemplary impact on the pupils in order to bring them closer to him, to urge them to follow the values of the country. And then it will be possible to send young people to a new field of activity that is useful, interesting and relevant for them. At the same time, the teacher should be able to enter their inner world without any coercion, i.e. decrees, orders, assignments, and enrich their spiritual world.

The growing influence of the social environment on the language and everyday speech, in turn, can lead to a drop in the human level. However, a high-level, pure, spiritualized language, in turn, can and should influence the improvement, spiritual enrichment and change its formation in

the environment. Therefore, at present, a deeper study of the features of the national language leads to effective results of the correct, complete formation of the literary language.

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